

Radiological Features and Clinical Presentation of Male Breast Cancer: A Retrospective Review

Sapna S Patel¹, Saumil Desai², Yash J Desai³, Mohd Ashraf⁴

¹Associate Professor, Department of Radio-diagnosis, GCRI, Ahmedabad. B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad

² Associate Professor, Department of Radio-diagnosis, GCRI, Ahmedabad. B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad

^{3,4}Resident, Department of Radio-diagnosis, GCRI, Ahmedabad. B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad

Received: 01-12-2024 / Revised: 20-12-2024 / Accepted: 24-12-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Saumil Desai

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objectives: This study aims to evaluate the radiological features and clinical presentation of male breast cancer (MBC), focusing on imaging findings, histopathological correlations, and the challenges of diagnosis.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of male patients diagnosed with MBC between August 2020 and June 2024 at tertiary care cancer centre. All patients presented with palpable breast masses and underwent a radiological workup, including mammography, ultrasonography, and computed tomography (CT). Imaging features such as size, shape, margins, and echogenicity of the masses were reviewed, and histopathological diagnosis was obtained through biopsy or surgical resection.

Results: Sixteen male patients with palpable breast masses were included. Mammographic findings revealed irregular masses with spiculated margins, while ultrasound showed hypoechoic, solid masses with irregular contours. Histopathological examination confirmed invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC) in all cases.

Conclusions: MBC typically presents as a palpable retro-areolar mass, and its diagnosis is often delayed, resulting in later-stage presentations. Invasive ductal carcinoma is the predominant histological type. Early detection, through improved awareness and targeted screening, is essential for improving clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Male breast cancer, imaging features, mammography, ultrasound, computed tomography, invasive ductal carcinoma.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Breast cancer is predominantly a disease of women, but male breast cancer (MBC) remains a rare yet clinically significant condition, accounting for approximately 0.7% of all breast cancers and 0.17% of all male cancers [1, 2]. MBC is frequently diagnosed at more advanced stages due to delayed presentation, lack of awareness, and the absence of routine screening for men. The most common histological type is invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC), representing 85-90% of cases [3].

MBC typically presents as a unilateral, painless, and often fixed sub areolar mass [4-6]. On mammography, these masses are often spiculated with irregular margins, while ultrasound typically shows hypoechoic solid masses with poorly defined borders. Although men lack the lobules and acini typical of invasive lobular carcinoma in women, IDC remains the predominant histologic subtype [4, 5].

This study aims to explore the radiological features and clinical presentation of MBC, emphasizing the

importance of early diagnosis and increased awareness of the condition

Methods:

This retrospective study included male patients who were diagnosed with MBC between August 2020 and June 2024 at tertiary care cancer centre. All patients presented with a palpable breast mass and were referred for imaging based on clinical suspicion of malignancy. The imaging modalities used were:

- Mammography: Craniocaudal (CC) and Medio-lateral oblique (MLO) views were obtained for all patients.
- Ultrasound: High-resolution ultrasound was performed to assess mass characteristics, including size, shape, margins, and echogenicity.
- Computed Tomography (CT): CT scans were employed in select cases for further evaluation of mass characteristics and adjacent tissue involvement.

Each mass was assessed according to the Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System (BI-RADS) lexicon, with a focus on the following features:

- Location, size, and shape
- Margin characteristics (e.g., spiculated, irregular, well-defined)
- Density and echogenicity
- Presence of micro calcifications or other associated findings (e.g., skin or nipple involvement)

Histopathological confirmation was obtained via biopsy (either core needle biopsy or excisional biopsy) for all cases, with the final diagnosis confirmed through histological examination.

Results

A total of 16 male patients were included in the study, all presenting with a palpable breast mass. The key findings from the radiological and histopathological evaluations are summarized below:

Patient Demographics: All patients were male, with an age range of 46 to 70 years. The majority (75%) were over 50 years of age, which is consistent with the typical age range for MBC diagnosis [7, 8].

Imaging Findings:

- **Mammography:** Among the eight patients who underwent mammography, all had masses with spiculated margins. In few cases, punctate micro calcifications were observed (12% of mammograms).
- **Ultrasound:** Ultrasound revealed hypoechoic solid masses with irregular margins in all 16 cases. No cystic or benign-appearing masses were identified.
- **CT:** For the four patients who underwent CT, lesions appeared as enhancing solid masses, with some cases showing involvement of the nipple-areolar complex and overlying skin.

Histopathology: Histopathological examination confirmed IDC in all 16 cases. Thirteen patients had a diagnosis confirmed via ultrasound-guided core needle biopsy, while three underwent surgical resection for definitive diagnosis.

Mass Location:

- 68% of the masses were located in the retro-areolar region.
- 32% were located eccentrically in other areas of the breast tissue

Figure 1: Mammogram of 46 years male with palpable mass in right breast on clinical examination, which after imaging and biopsy showed Invasive ductal carcinoma on histopathology. Right craniocaudal (CC) and Right medio-lateral oblique view (MLO) showing well defined radiopaque mass with irregular margins in outer central region in right breast. No e/o calcification / nipple retraction seen.

Figure 2: Mammogram of 52 years male patient with palpable mass in left breast on initial presentation. It shows ill-defined radiopaque mass with spiculated margins seen in retro-areolar region in left breast on LCC and L-MLO view. Nipple retraction is appreciable. No calcification appreciated. Histopathology confirmed Invasive ductal carcinoma.

Figure 3: Mammogram of a 70 years male with palpable mass in right breast. It shows ill-defined radiopaque mass with irregular margins in upper outer quadrant of right breast on RCC and R-MLO view. Multiple tiny foci of calcifications seen. Histopathology confirmed Invasive ductal carcinoma.

Figure 4: Mammogram of a 70-year male with palpable mass and exophytic component which was noted on clinical examination in left breast. It shows well-defined lobulated radiopaque mass seen in retro-areolar region in left breast on LCC and L-MLO view. Few tiny foci of calcifications are seen. Nipple areolar complex appears involved by mass. Lesion shows exophytic component. Histopathology confirmed Invasive ductal carcinoma.

Figure 5: Contrast enhanced CT scan (axial view) of a 62-year male with palpable mass in right breast. It shows well-defined enhancing mass lesion in retro-areolar region in right breast/chest wall. Nipple areolar complex appears to be involved by mass. Overlying skin thickened on the lesion margins and involved by lesion. Histopathology confirmed Invasive ductal carcinoma.

Discussion:

Although male breast cancer is rare, it is a clinically significant condition that requires heightened

awareness among healthcare providers. MBC typically affects men between 60 and 70 years of age, a decade later than in women [7, 8]. As

observed in this study, IDC is the most common histological type of MBC, consistent with the findings of other studies [4, 9].

The lack of routine breast cancer screening in men and the relatively limited amount of breast tissue compared to women often lead to delayed diagnoses. By the time most cases are detected, they are typically in more advanced stages, with palpable, fixed masses being the most common presenting symptom. In the absence of screening programs, early-stage MBC is often missed until the patient presents with a palpable mass or other symptoms.

Imaging plays a critical role in the diagnosis of MBC. Mammography typically shows irregular or spiculated masses, a feature that raises suspicion for malignancy. Ultrasound is an effective and less costly alternative, often used for further evaluation and biopsy guidance. In our study, ultrasound was the primary diagnostic tool, and it provided clarity for diagnosis and biopsy in all cases. CT scans were used selectively to evaluate more complex cases, particularly those with suspected involvement of adjacent structures.

Given the relatively low incidence of MBC, many radiologists may not be as familiar with its radiologic presentation. This emphasizes the need for ongoing education and awareness regarding MBC among clinicians, radiologists, and patients alike.

Conclusion

Male breast cancer, though rare, typically presents as a palpable retro-areolar mass and is often diagnosed at more advanced stages due to delayed presentation. Invasive ductal carcinoma remains the predominant histological type. Radiological modalities such as mammography and ultrasound are essential for diagnosing MBC, and early detection is crucial for improving patient outcomes. Increased awareness, targeted screening efforts, and patient education are necessary to facilitate earlier diagnosis and intervention.

References

1. Giordano SH. A review of the diagnosis and management of male breast cancer. *Oncologist* 2005; 10:471-479.
2. Applebaum AH, Evans GF, Levy KR, et al. Mammographic appearances of male breast disease. *Radiographics* 1999; 19:559-568.
3. Brinton LA, Cook MB, McCormack V, et al. Anthropometric and Hormonal Risk Factors for Male Breast Cancer: Male Breast Cancer Pooling Project Results. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute* 2014.
4. Erhan Y, Zekioglu O, Erhan Y. Invasive Lobular Carcinoma of the Male Breast. *Can J Surg* 2006; 49(5):365-6.
5. Yildirim E, Berberoğlu U. Male breast cancer: a 22-year experience. *Eur J Surg Oncol* 1998; 24:548-52.
6. American College of Radiology (ACR) ACR Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System (BI-RADS) 4th ed. Reston, VA: American College of Radiology, 2003.
7. Nguyen C, et al. Male breast disease: pictorial review with radiologic-pathologic correlation. *Radiographics* 2013; 33:763-79.
8. Sanguinetti A, et al. Male breast cancer, clinical presentation, diagnosis and treatment: Twenty years of experience in our Breast Unit. *Int J Surg Case Rep* 2016; 20S:8-11.
9. Yildirim E, Berberoğlu U. Male breast cancer: a 22-year experience. *Eur J Surg Oncol* 1998; 24:548-52.
10. Yang WT, et al. Sonographic features of primary breast cancer in men. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 2001; 176:413-6.
11. Dershaw DD, et al. Mammographic findings in men with breast cancer. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 1993; 160:267-70.
12. Partik B, et al. Malignant and benign diseases of the breast in 41 male patients: mammography, sonography, and pathohistological correlations. *Rofo* 2001; 173:1012-8.